

Original Research

Organisational Culture and Job Satisfaction in Local Government Authorities: Insights from Human Resources for Health in Tanzania

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Abstract

This study examined the influence of organisational culture on job satisfaction among human resources for health in Local Government Authorities in Dodoma City, Tanzania. A study on organizational culture and job satisfaction is essential for designing human resources for health policies and satisfaction strategies that fit workers' perceptions from the health sector. Using cross-sectional design, the study collected data from a sample of 230 human resources for health. The study collected quantitative and qualitative data using survey questionnaire and interview methods respectively. Quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics and binary logistic regression. The qualitative data from the key informants were analysed through content analysis. Descriptive findings indicate that there is job dissatisfaction among human resources for health in Dodoma. The findings denote that human resources for health are mainly dissatisfied with their salary, recognition, achievement, supervision, and job content in the LGAs. Also, the study findings reveal that organizational values, taboos, and structure significantly influence job satisfaction. Specifically, high alignment with organizational values (AOR=1.257, $p=0.0354$), strong influence of organizational taboos (AOR=1.433, $p=0.0175$), and organizational structure (AOR=1.861, $p=0.0266$) were associated with higher job satisfaction. Similarly, the findings add that organizational culture aspects, namely open communication, freedom of speech, mutual respect and welcoming newcomers, influence positively job satisfaction. The study concludes that certain aspects of the organizational culture influence job satisfaction. It is recommended that the Local Government Authorities in Tanzania, including Dodoma City, should develop recognition programs to acknowledge and reward employee contributions.

Keywords: Human Resource for Health, Job satisfaction, Local Government Authorities, Organization culture.

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Introduction

Organisational culture is an increasingly important area in the field of management and administration. Scholars acknowledge that organization culture influences organisational behavior, goals, work methods, interaction norms and interpersonal connections (Akpa et al., 2021). Also, organisational culture builds a sense of purpose and unity among employees for accomplishing a complex and challenging job environment (Andres et al., 2019). Thus, organisational culture enables public institutions such as Local Government Authorities (LGAs) to have skilled and experience employees to perform better and offer quality service to the beneficiaries.

Pathiranage and Jayatilake (2020) defined organisational culture as the collection of shared meanings, norms, values, beliefs and practices among members that influence how they behave. Akpa et al. (2021) add that organisational culture shapes organizational behavior of how and when, who and how things are done and the connection between people. Also, Jigjiddorj et al. (2021) opine that organizational culture is all about shared beliefs and values as established by the founders and communicated through different ways. Importantly, organizational culture builds staff morale and leadership to increase job satisfaction, which leads to greater job performance (Paais & Pattiruhu, 2020).

In organisations that are eager in providing better services applies some efforts in improving the organizational culture to satisfy employees. The high levels of job satisfaction contribute to a motivated and committed workforce. In health care sector which provides a lot of employment opportunity; job satisfaction is observed as the key aspect that needs to be considered due to its impact on the effective functioning of the health system (Msacky & Assey, 2024). Smith and Johnson (2023) highlight that job satisfaction is important to the healthcare sector since it directly influences the quality of care provided to patients, staff retention rates and overall health outcomes.

Scholars in in the field of public administration and health portray that job satisfaction is the emotional response one has about various components of his or job (Lee & Kim, 2024; Cantarelli, et al., 2023; Armstrong, 2020). Studies show that job satisfaction affects work performance, work absenteeism, and job turnover (Montuori et al., 2022; Geta et al., 2021; Dhamija et al., 2018). It is also noted that job satisfaction has a significant impact on perceived health, family connections, and social relationships, all of which contribute to overall life quality. A significant percentage of the world's 1 billion full-time workers are disengaged, according to recent Gallup data on job satisfaction. The Gallup data show that globally only 15% of workers report being content and productive at work, while the remaining 47% report being psychologically detached from their jobs and employers (Montuori et al., 2022).

Reviewed studies have highlighted the universal importance of organisational culture in creating job satisfaction, which, in turn, improves organizational performance and employee well-being in a variety of cultural and sectoral contexts. A study in the United States found that a supportive organizational culture boosts employee engagement and trust (Meng & Berger, 2019). In India, scholars investigated job satisfaction and quality of life indicators among bank employees. The findings show that a strong organisational

culture that encourages free speech and courteous oversight considerably increases employee satisfaction (Dhamija et al., 2018).

Similarly, Sutoro (2020) examined factors influencing job satisfaction among teachers in Indonesia, demonstrating that organisational culture directly impacts job satisfaction. This study emphasized the importance of a workplace culture that promotes positive attitudes and behaviors, cultivates a supportive work environment, and underscores professionalism. In another context, Lee and Kim (2024) conducted a comparative study in South Korea, examining the impact of organisational culture on job satisfaction in public and private sector organizations. This study emphasized the importance of tailoring cultural initiatives to meet employees' unique needs in different sectors, enhancing job satisfaction and organisational effectiveness.

The findings from different countries and sectors underscore a universal connection between organizational culture and job satisfaction. This is to say that when employees feel satisfied with their job, it not only enhances their professional and personal well-being but also translates into tangible benefits for the organization (Mongi, 2020). Tanzania is among the countries that focuses in improving its services by embarking on several initiatives that aim to enhance job satisfaction and organizational culture within the health sector. The notable efforts include the implementation of Health Sector Reforms in the 1990s and Local Government Reform Programme (LGRP) in 1998, which decentralize health services delivery to Local Government Authorities (LGAs), including Dodoma City, to plan, execute, and monitor health service delivery at district hospitals, health centers, and dispensaries (Kigume & Maluka, 2018). The reforms were part of the major economic and social reforms started in the mid-1980s in most developing countries (Kessy, 2018). It is noted that reforms in Tanzania transfer resources including human resource for health and powers to more autonomous LGAs (Tidemand & Msami, 2010). As a result of reforms, the Ministry of the President's Office of Regional Authority and Local Government (PORALG) was charged with the responsibility of overseeing the delivery of Primary Health Care (PHC), i.e. dispensaries, health centres and district hospitals, including management of human resources for health. Similarly, in 2018, Tanzania introduced Direct Health Facility Financing (DHFF). The DHFF channels funds directly to individual health facilities to improve health system performance, including satisfaction of human resources for health (Ruhago et al., 2023; Abdu & Nzilano, 2018).

It is noted that human resources for health in Tanzania under the LGAs experience various challenges, including inadequate remuneration, insufficient resources, poor working conditions, limited opportunities for professional development, poor quality services, and high patient-to-staff ratios (Msacky, 2024; Chilipweli et al., 2023; Mongi, 2020; Kigume & Maluka, 2018; Kessy, 2018). The unaddressed challenges may result in high labour turnover, deterioration of service delivery and a dissatisfied workforce in the health sector. Also, the persistence of health service delivery challenges in LGAs, including Dodoma City, may affect employees' retention and health service performance.

Most reviewed studies in the context of organizational culture and job satisfaction among human resources for health were done in countries like South Korea, China, Spain; Indonesia, Ethiopia, United States of America, and Bangladesh (Lee & Kim, 2024; Alehegn, 2023; Smith & Johnson, 2023; Garcia & Martinez, 2022; Geta et al., 2021;

Cheng & Wang, 2021; Jigjiddorj et al., 2021; Mesfin et al., 2020; Ahmedet al., 2015). Also, in the same context some other studies dwelt on organizational culture and performance in the sectors of banking and education (Akpa et al., 2021; Paaïs & Pattiruhu, 2020; Sutoro, 2020; Meng & Berger, 2019). Likewise, studies on satisfaction from Tanzania had their attention on teachers and students in the education sector (Mrope, 2023; Mashenene, 2019). Thus, there is inadequate of studies that focus on organizational culture and job satisfaction in the health sector from Tanzania. Studies on country specific like Tanzania with its historical background of socialism and self-reliance and decentralization is required to capture particular features and norms of people in enhancing job satisfaction. Also, a study like this is essential for designing human resource for health policies and satisfaction strategies that fit workers perception from the health sector. Similarly, this study seeks to provide valuable insights that can inform policymakers to enhance human resources for health management strategies, improve employee morale, retention, and overall quality, leading to better healthcare outcomes. Therefore, this study is set to examine the influence of organizational culture on job satisfaction among health workers in Local Government Authorities at Dodoma City, Tanzania.

Literature review

The study employed Herzberg's Two Factor Theory as a framework to understand job satisfaction in the cultural setting like LGAs in Tanzania. Frederick Herzberg originated the hypothesis in the 1950s. The theory has shown that job dissatisfaction is mostly related to the working environment, but job satisfaction is tied to the nature of the work itself (Gupta, 2022). The Herzberg's Two Factor Theory is built on the assumption that work related aspects termed as satisfiers or motivators in organization when present such as a sense of accomplishment, personal growth prospects for professional development, responsibility, and opportunities for promotion and career advancement all contribute to job satisfaction and enhanced performance (Armstrong, 2020). However, their absence does not necessarily result in displeasure. Hygiene variables such as business policy, norms, technical supervision, quality of supervision, management support, interpersonal interactions, income remuneration for work accomplished, job security, working conditions, status do not typically lead to job satisfaction, but their absence can cause dissatisfaction.

Based on the satisfiers and hygiene variables, the theory becomes limited to the internal aspects of the organisation, such as organisational culture, which is related to the organization's policy and norms. Moreover, individuals vary in nature and may find satisfaction in different ways. It is not necessary for satisfying factors identified in this theory to be the same for all people because a hygiene factor to one person may be a motivational factor to another person (Gupta, 2022). Despite the noted limitations the assumptions of the theory revolve around specific aspects of organization culture and job satisfaction such as policy, norms, and salary which are all important in informing the study. Also, Herzberg's theory remains useful and has been employed by various scholars in their research. Scholars, Szydho and Buklaho (2020), Msacky and Assey (2024), have demonstrated the theory's applicability in literature review, data presentation, and discussion, underscoring its relevance in understanding job satisfaction among human resources for health in LGAs.

Similarly, previous scholars have emphasized the importance of tailoring cultural initiatives to meet the unique needs of employees in different sectors, so as to enhance job satisfaction and organizational effectiveness (Garcia & Martinez, 2022). Meng and Berger (2019) conducted a study in the United States, focusing on the impact of organizational culture on job satisfaction among public relations professionals. Their findings revealed a positive correlation between organizational culture and employee engagement and trust. Although the direct relationship with job satisfaction was not explicitly established, the study underscored the importance of a supportive organizational culture in fostering employee well-being and commitment.

Similarly, Smith and Johnson (2023) explored the impact of organizational culture on job satisfaction across various industries in the United States. They identified a significant positive correlation between organizational culture and job satisfaction. Employees who perceived a supportive and positive organizational culture reported higher levels of job satisfaction, highlighting the crucial role of organizational culture in enhancing employee well-being and organizational performance. In China, Chen and Wang (2021) delved into the mediating role of organizational culture in the relationship between leadership style and job satisfaction. Their study revealed that transformational leadership was positively associated with a supportive organizational culture, which, in turn, enhanced job satisfaction among employees.

In Spain, Garcia and Martinez (2022) conducted a longitudinal study among healthcare professionals to explore the role of organizational culture in job satisfaction. Their findings indicated that changes in organizational culture significantly influenced job satisfaction over time. This is to say that improved organizational culture were associated with increased job satisfaction among healthcare professionals, underscoring the dynamic nature of organizational culture and its impact on employee well-being. Lastly, Lee and Kim (2024) conducted a comparative study in South Korea, examining the impact of organizational culture on job satisfaction in public and private sector organizations. Their findings revealed sector-specific differences in the cultural dimensions that influenced job satisfaction. While both sectors benefited from a positive organizational culture, public sector employees prioritized stability and bureaucracy, while private sector employees valued innovation and flexibility.

Material and methods

To guarantee a thorough grasp of the influence of organizational culture on job satisfaction among health workers in LGAs, the study adopted a quantitative and qualitative approach for data collecting and analysis. This method's main benefit is that it collects a solid set of data by combining quantitative and qualitative methodologies. The data collected from 230 respondents was gathered using a cross-sectional design. This design was opted given its ability to permit data collection at one point in time of job satisfaction and organisational culture among human resource for health.

The study was conducted at Dodoma City in Tanzania. Dodoma City was selected purposely from among the LGAs in Tanzania because of its sharp increase in population after the government shifted its capital from Dar Es Salaam City to Dodoma (Msacky

&Assey, 2024). The population increase is expected to increase the demand for health services in Dodoma City. Also, the increase in population is presumed to increase the demand for human resources for health and working equipment in health facilities. A report from the National Bureau of Statistics affirms that the population of Dodoma City has increased from 410,956 in 2012 to 765,179 in 2022. Thus, the rapid increase in population has resulted in a high demand for health services, which impacts health workers' workload and job satisfaction.

The study's target population comprised health workers from several healthcare facilities in Dodoma City. This population includes the heads of the healthcare facilities, doctors, nurses, administrative workers, and support staff to ensure a complete representation of the workforce dealing with health services in Dodoma City. The sample size for the study was computed using Yamane's (1967) statistical formula. This statistical formula gives a 95% confidence level with 5% precision to estimate. Equation 1 expresses this formula: n denotes the sample size, N signifies the population size, and e represents the precision level (sampling error). Thus, the formula is expressed as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)} = \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where: n = sample size, N = population size, and e = margin of error (often expressed as a decimal, e.g., 0.05 for 5%). Yamane's (1967) formula is widely used when working with a define populations with a specified level of precision.

$$\frac{541}{1 + 541 \times (0.05)^2} = 229.96 \approx 230$$

Previous studies (Mrope, 2023 sampled 126; Jigjiddorj et al., 2021 sampled 180; Mongi, 2020 sampled 100; Paais & Pattiruhu, 2020 sampled 155; Ahamed et al., 2015 sampled 36) on organisational culture and job satisfaction were successfully conducted with the sample ranged between 36 to 180. The human resources for health who participated in the survey were selected using simple random sampling from the healthcare facilities of Dodoma City. Also, the study selected 9 key informants using purposive sampling. The key informants were mainly the heads of the healthcare facilities. Similarly, a total of 8 healthcare facilities from Dodoma City were purposively selected. The data were collected from the key informants using the interview method. The key informants provided valuable qualitative data that complemented the quantitative survey results.

Regarding the data collection methods and tools, quantitative data was collected through structured questionnaires distributed to 230 human resources for health. This method provided numerical data that were statistically analysed to identify trends and patterns. The design of the questionnaires was based on a closed-ended five-Likert scale to capture specific aspects of organisational culture and job satisfaction. Also, qualitative data from the key informants was collected through interviews. The heads of healthcare facilities were asked to give their opinions about the organization's culture and job satisfaction.

Then, data were analysed using quantitative and qualitative techniques. The quantitative data was descriptively and inferentially analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. The descriptive analysis was presented in the form of means, standard deviations, and percentages to examine the quantitative data pattern. It involved presenting the demographic characteristics of the respondents and their responses to each item on the survey, providing an overall picture of the sample and the general trends in job satisfaction and perceptions of organizational culture.

Also, further analysis of the quantitative techniques adopted inferential statistics of the variables. Inferential statistics, including chi-square tests and binary logistic regression were used to examine the relationships between organizational culture and job satisfaction. The chi square test was carried out to determine aspects to be included in the model. Regression analysis determined the strength and direction of these relationships, providing insights into which aspects of organisational culture had the most significant impact on job satisfaction. The binary response was possible after transforming the five Likert scale aspects of dependent variable into two responses: satisfied and dissatisfied human resource for health using the overall mean score. The transformation of the five Likert scale into two responses was adopted from previous studies (Msacky, 2024; Mashenene, 2019). Subsequently, dichotomous responses for human resource for health job satisfaction was created where 0 represented satisfied employees and 1 dissatisfied employees. The binary logistic regression equation (2) used for this analysis is as follows:

$$\log it[\pi(x)] = \log\left(\frac{\pi(x)}{1-\pi(x)}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \dots + \beta_p x_p \quad (2)$$

Where $\pi(x)$ is the likelihood of job satisfaction among human resources for health. The x_i 's are set of independent variables (norms, values, behaviour, taboos and organisation structure) and β_i 's represent parameter estimates or logit coefficients.

The findings from the model were presented in a regression in the form of an Unadjusted Odds Ratio (UOR) and Adjusted Odds Ratio (AOR). The fitness of the model was tested using the Hosmer and Lemeshow Test. Normally, Hosmer and Lemeshow's statistical test shows a poor fit if the significance value is less than ($P < 0.05$). Also, Hosmer and Lemeshow's statistical test shows a good fit if the significance value is greater than ($P > 0.05$) at 95 confidence interval. The statistical tests ensured that the model accurately represented the data and could be used to draw valid conclusions about the relationships between variables. Similarly, the qualitative data from key informant interviews were analysed by content analysis. This method is particularly useful in studying complex phenomena and complement quantitative results, providing a deeper understanding of the organization culture's influence on job satisfaction.

The study used Cronbach's Alpha (α) to assess the internal consistency of the tool. Cronbach Alpha values provide the following rule of thumb: $\alpha \geq 0.9$: Excellent; $0.8 \leq \alpha < 0.9$: Good; $0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$: Acceptable; $0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$: Questionable; $0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$: Poor; $\alpha < 0.5$: Unacceptable. Thus, based on the rule of thumb, the reliability for the study is above 0.7. The α value scores in Table 1 render the reliability of the study tool as good and acceptable.

Table 1. Reliability statistics

Objective	No. Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Results
Organization Culture	05	.833	Good
Job satisfaction	07	.735	Acceptable
Overall	12	.783	Acceptable

Findings and discussion

This section aimed to present the findings and provide a discussion on the influence of organisational culture on job satisfaction among health workers in Local Government Authorities at Dodoma. The study findings are quantitatively and qualitatively analyzed. The quantitative analysis uses descriptive and inferential techniques. The qualitative findings complemented the quantitative data. This section is divided into subsections: job satisfaction for human resource health, the association between variables, and the influence of organisation culture on job satisfaction.

Job satisfaction and human resources for health

Table 2 presents the job satisfaction of human resources for health from Dodoma City using descriptive statistics. Job satisfaction was assessed based on seven items: salary, recognition, achievement, supervision, job security, opportunities for growth, and job content. The findings show that the overall mean score for all the job satisfaction aspects was 2.90. Hence, the mean scores for specific aspects, including salary, recognition, achievement, supervision, and job content, were below the overall mean. This category could be associated with dissatisfied employees with their jobs. Also, the findings show that job security and opportunities for growth aspects were above the overall mean. The overall mean score for job satisfaction was calculated as done in studies by Lu et al. (2016), Chilipweli et al. (2023) and Geta et al. (2021). Thus, the aspects from the overall mean and above were categorised as satisfied employees. The findings suggest that employees are generally dissatisfied with their jobs.

Table 2. Respondent perceptions of job satisfaction

Variable	Mean±Std
Fair salary for the work	2.72±1.23
Recognition for the contribution	2.83±1.18
Achievement	2.81±1.27
Supervision and guidance	2.88±1.22
Job security	2.90±1.25
Opportunity for growth	3.24±1.42
Job content	2.77±1.29
Overall	2.90±0.81

Association between variables

This sub-section used the Chi-square test to establish the association between variables of the study. This test was carried out to identify aspects to be included in the binary

logistic regression model. Table 3 presents the factors associated with job satisfaction based on the chi-square test. The findings show that job satisfaction is statistically significantly associated with the type of health facility where an employee works ($p=0.0173$) and statistically insignificantly associated with organisational culture ($p=0.0637$). The findings show that satisfied health workers were from health centres (25.37%), followed by dispensaries (11.54%). Similarly, the findings show that a large proportion of human resources for health are dissatisfied with organisational culture (76.98%). Thus, the findings in Table 3 imply that organisational culture is insignificantly associated with job satisfaction. The local government authorities need to ensure that continuous efforts are directed toward enhancing organisational culture to achieve high levels of employee job satisfaction.

Table 3. Factors associated with Job satisfaction among healthcare workers

Variable	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Chi-square	P-Value
Type of health facility			8.1162	0.0173
District Hospital	63(90.00)	7(10.00)		
Health Center	100(74.63)	34(25.37)		
Dispensary	23(88.46)	3(11.54)		
Occupation			4.7447	0.6911
Medical Doctor	9(64.29)	5(35.71)		
Clinical officer	31(83.78)	6(16.22)		
Nurse	46(77.97)	13(22.03)		
Pharmacist	17(89.47)	2(10.53)		
Medical attendant	17(77.27)	5(22.73)		
Laboratory technician	26(83.87)	5(16.13)		
Health officer	14(87.50)	2(12.50)		
Others	26(81.25)	6(18.75)		
Sex			1.0413	0.3075
Male	57(77.03)	17(22.97)		
Female	129(82.69)	27(17.31)		
Age of respondent			2.2810	0.3197
2035	116(78.38)	32(21.62)		
3650	64(86.49)	10(13.51)		
51 and above	6(75.00)	2(25.00)		
Education qualification			0.2455	0.8845
Secondary	9(81.82)	2(18.18)		
University/college	176(80.73)	42(19.27)		
Other	1(100.00)	0(0.00)		
Organization culture			3.4383	0.0637
Low	79(86.81)	12(13.19)		
High	107(76.98)	32(23.02)		

The Influence of organization culture on job satisfaction among health workers

The study used binary logistic regression to assess the influence of organization culture variables on job satisfaction. After adjusting the variables, the analysis revealed that several factors significantly influenced job satisfaction. The findings in Table 4 show that employees who align with the organisation's values are more likely to have higher job satisfaction (AOR=1.257, p=0.0354). It is further indicated that employees with high experience of taboos in the organisation are more likely to have higher job satisfaction (AOR=1.433, p=0.0175). Similarly, the findings reported that employees who perceive a high organisational structure are more likely to have higher job satisfaction (AOR=1.861, p=0.0266) than those with low organisational structure experience. Therefore, findings in Table 4 indicate that higher levels of organizational values, taboos, and organization structure are associated with increased job satisfaction among employees under LGAs in the health sector.

Table 4. Binary Logistics for organization culture on job satisfaction

Variables	OR [95% CI]	P-value	AOR [95% CI]	p-value
Low Norms Ref				
High Norms	0.963[0.818,1.654]	0.3989	0.765[0.425,1.332]	0.4143
Low values Ref				
High Values	1.634[1.089,2.453]	0.0178	1.257[1.075,2.039]	0.0354
Low behavior Ref				
High Behaviors	1.437[0.994,2.077]	0.0539	0.939[0.579,1.520]	0.7965
Low Taboos Ref				
High Taboos	1.918[1.257,2.929]	0.0025	1.433[1.052,2.411]	0.0175
Low org structure Ref				
High Organization structure	2.260[1.393,3.666]	0.0010	1.861[1.075,3.223]	0.0266
Hosmer and Lemeshow test: 0.0924 Chi-square test = 8.643, df=8 and P-value=0.472				

The findings affirm that values, taboos, and organisational culture significantly influence job satisfaction among health workers in Local Government Authorities in Dodoma City. The findings align with Sutoro's (2020) research in Indonesia, which showed that values, behaviours, and attitudes directly affect job satisfaction. Dhamija et al. (2018) also found that organisational culture enhances job satisfaction by fostering freedom of speech, respect, and belongingness. Similarly, Paais and Pattiruhu (2020) highlighted that organisational culture positively impacts performance and job satisfaction.

Moreover, Table 5 provides additional evidence confirming that organisation culture significantly influences job satisfaction after controlling other variables of the demographic factors that were significant in Table 3. The findings in Table 5 revealed that the health workers with high organisational culture were nearly twice as likely to be satisfied compared to those with low organizational culture (AOR=1.604, p=0.0271). The findings underscore the importance of fostering a strong organisational culture to enhance job satisfaction among health workers.

Table 5. Binary logistic regression factors associated with job satisfaction

Variable	Unadjusted		Adjusted	
	Or [95% Ci]	P-Value	Aor [95% Ci]	P-Value
Type of health facility				
Dispensary	Ref		Ref	
Health Center	3.060[1.279,7.321]	0.0120	1.745[0.682,4.465]	0.2456
District Hospital	1.174[0.280,4.926]	0.8266	0.875[0.198,3.854]	0.8594
Organization culture				
Low	Ref		Ref	
High	1.969[0.954,4.063]	0.0668	1.604[1.145,3.451]	0.0271

The findings concur with previous research by Mesfin et al. (2020), which demonstrated a positive association between organisation culture and job satisfaction, suggesting the need for cultural transformation to enhance job satisfaction. Similarly, Ahamed and Mahmood (2015) found a significant positive relationship between organisational culture and job satisfaction. The findings suggest the importance of continually emphasising high organisation culture at workplaces to improve job satisfaction.

The general impression of organizational culture and job satisfaction analysed in this study is further reiterated by the qualitative findings showing that most respondents believe that open communication, freedom of speech, and mutual respect are key factors that enhance employees' job satisfaction. Additionally, most informants noted that a welcoming culture for newcomers, including counselling and adaptation support, contributes positively to their job satisfaction. The key informants added that values, norms, and behaviours significantly contribute to job satisfaction by serving as guiding principles in the workplace. Providing examples, key informants described how their initial discomfort at a new health facility was alleviated by a welcoming culture that included counselling and adaptation support for newcomers. Moreover, the key informants added that organisational culture increases not only job satisfaction but also employee retention, performance, and loyalty to employers. Similarly, the interviewees highlighted that a high organisational culture attracts new employees of high calibre, skills, and experience to the working environment of the health sector in the LGA. The findings are supported by Jigjiddorj et al. (2021), who also concluded that positive organisational culture enhances job satisfaction. Therefore, fostering a strong organisational culture ensures committed, satisfied employees and reduces turnover.

The interpretation and discussion of the presented findings should consider some limitations linked to this study. The study was limited to only one urban council in Dodoma City in Tanzania; therefore, the findings may not be generalizable to all the councils and health workers across Tanzania, with different organisational cultures and health system structures. Additionally, the data collection relied on self-reported measures of job satisfaction and perceptions of organization culture, which may have been subject to social desirability bias or inaccurate self-assessment. Furthermore, the transformation of the Likert scale into a binary format might have excluded neutral responses. In the same context, several independent variables including organisation culture, leadership style, worklife balance, cultural diversity and technological

development are cited as important in influencing job satisfaction (Canatarelli, et al., 2023; Geta, et al., 2021; Cheng & Wang, 2021; Armstrong, 2020; Gupta, 2020 & Abdu, et al., 20218). However, it is not all the independent variables were considered in this study. This study used mainly the organisation culture to predict its influence on job satisfaction among human resources for health. The identified limitations are important in bolstering the recommendations in the subsequent section. Despite the limitations noted, this study contributes theoretically by applying Herzberg's Two-Factor theory to understand job satisfaction within the cultural context of Local Government Authorities (LGAs) in Tanzania. Also, this study adds to the empirical evidence on the influence of organisation culture on the outcome variable, such as job satisfaction among human resources for health in LGAs.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study focused on organisational culture and job satisfaction among human resources for health in LGAs of Dodoma City. Findings posit that human resources for health in Local Government Authorities at Dodoma City are dissatisfied with their job. This conclusion is based on the descriptive statistics for overall job satisfaction for various job satisfaction aspects. Also, the study concludes that high organisation culture in terms of values, taboos and organisational structure is significantly associated with job satisfaction among human resources for health. Moreover, the findings establish that organisation culture aspects, namely open communication, freedom of speech, mutual respect and welcoming newcomers, contribute positively to job satisfaction.

Based on the evidence generated in this study, the Local Government Authorities in Dodoma City should develop recognition programs to acknowledge and reward employee contributions, thereby improving their sense of achievement and job satisfaction. Also, the government through the ministry of President's and Local Government (PO–RALG) and ministry of health should provide training to supervisors of the healthcare facilities to improve their leadership skills for offering supportive and constructive guidance to health workers. Similarly, employees and employers in the LGAs should promote a culture of open communication, respect, and inclusivity. Likewise, the LGAs to encourage values and norms that align with employees' expectations and enhance their sense of belonging and job satisfaction.

Considering areas for further research, it is recommended that future studies focus on urban and rural LGAs to generalize the findings in Tanzania. Also, future researchers may concentrate on other variables, namely leadership style, work-life balance, and technological development, that affect job satisfaction. Studies on highlighted variables may provide valuable insights and contribute to the development of strategies to enhance job satisfaction.

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